

SELF-HEALING POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Thermosetting polymers, used in a wide variety of applications ranging from microelectronics to composite airplane wings, are susceptible to damage in the form of cracking. Often these cracks form deep within the structure where detection is difficult and repair is virtually impossible. Inspired by biological systems in which damage triggers a healing response, a new structural polymeric material was recently developed [1] with the ability to *autonomically* heal cracks. Whenever damage occurs in a self-healing polymer, the repair process is triggered and after sufficient healing time, the inherent strength and toughness of the material is recovered. Self-healing polymers are designed to heal the microcracks that occur naturally during fatigue, thereby preventing large-scale cracks from forming. As a result, the fatigue life of these materials is expected to be significantly extended.

The self-healing concept is shown in Figure 1. A microencapsulated healing agent is embedded along with a catalyst into a polymer matrix. When damage occurs in the polymer a crack propagates through the matrix rupturing the microcapsules in the crack path. The ruptured microcapsules release the healing agent which is then drawn into the crack through capillary action. Once the healing agent within the crack plane comes into contact with the embedded catalyst, a chemical reaction is triggered and polymerization of the healing agent occurs. Afterwards, the crack faces are bonded and the strong singularity at the crack tip is relieved. Experiments on fracture specimens have yielded as much as 90% recovery of virgin toughness. This work will lead to safer and more reliable materials in a wide range of applications and represents the first step in developing materials systems that possess greatly extended lifetimes.

Figure 1. The self-healing concept in which a microencapsulated healing agent and catalyst are embedded within a structural polymer matrix.

INTRODUCTION

The natural process of fatigue in brittle polymers and composite leads to microcracking and other forms of micro-damage [2-6]. Eventually these microcracks coalesce to form large-scale cracks that propagate and lead to ultimate failure. The traditional approach to these problems has been to increase the inherent toughness of brittle polymers through addition of reinforcement phases or elastomers, or to repair the article once the cracks are large and of a critical size.

A new *self-healing* materials system was developed at the University of Illinois [1,7-12] and offers an alternative to these traditional approaches. Whenever damage occurs in a self-healing polymer, the repair process is triggered and after sufficient healing time, the inherent strength and toughness of the material is recovered. Self-healing polymers are designed to heal the microcracks that occur naturally during fatigue, thereby preventing large-scale cracks from forming. As a result, the fatigue life and the useful mechanical function of these materials are expected to be significantly extended.

MANUFACTURING PROCEDURE

Self-healing polymers are created in a two-step process beginning with the microencapsulation of the healing agent. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the microencapsulation procedure. An emulsion of the healing agent (dicyclopentadiene, DCPD) is created with an aqueous solution of urea and formaldehyde. In situ polymerization occurs at the DCPD surface at controlled temperature and pH. The emulsion is agitated throughout the process and the size of the capsules can be controlled by the agitation rate. Typically, we obtain 100-200 μm microcapsules at 450 rpm at 50°C and 3.5 pH.

Figure 2. Microencapsulation Procedure. An emulsion of dicyclopentadiene (core) is created with urea and formaldehyde and water. In-situ polymerization of urea-formaldehyde occurs at the surface of the DCPD cores and continues under controlled temperature and pH.

Once the microcapsules are prepared they are mixed with the polymer matrix. For the examples which follow, a bisphenol-A epoxide (EPON 828) was used along with a tetra-functional amine curing agent (DETA). The microcapsules are mixed with the epoxide prepolymer at 10 wt.% (total). The catalyst (Grubbs' catalyst)¹ [13] is then added at a typical concentration of 2.5 wt.% (total). The mixture is degassed and the curing agent is then added. The resin mixture is next poured into a mold and cured at room temperature for 24 h followed by a postcure of 40°C for 24 h. Figure 3 shows an example self-healing fracture toughness specimen after manufacture.

HEALING EFFICIENCY

Based on the work of Jud and Kausch [14] and Wool and O'Connor [15] we define the *healing efficiency* as,

$$\eta = \frac{K_{IC}^{healed}}{K_{IC}^{virgin}} \quad (1)$$

where K_{IC} is the critical mode-I stress intensity factor. A ratio of unity indicates complete recovery after healing. The healing efficiency depends on a number of factors including the concentration of catalyst and healing agent, the healing kinetics, the diffusion rate of the healing agent in the polymer matrix, the

¹ Grubbs' catalyst is a Ruthenium transition metal catalyst that initiates a ring-opening metathesis polymerization of the DCPD healing agent.

Figure 3. Self-Healing Polymer Specimen. NOTE: The geometry of the fracture toughness sample is designed for controlled crack propagation along the centerline of the sample and constant compliance with increasing crack length.

capillary pressure in the crack plane, the adhesive bond strength between the healing agent and polymer matrix, etc. An example result from a fracture toughness test is included in Figure 4. A fracture toughness sample similar to the one shown in Figure 3 was loaded in mode-I and a starter crack was propagated along the centerline of the specimen. The curve labeled “virgin” corresponds to the load-deflection data obtained for this test. Subsequently, the specimen was unloaded and allowed to heal for a total of 48 hours. The specimen was then reloaded to failure and the load-deflection data labeled “healed” was obtained. Analysis of the fracture data reveals that the healing efficiency for this specimen is approximately 90%.

Figure 4. Self-Healing Fracture Toughness Results. (a) A virgin specimen similar to that shown in Figure 3 is loaded to failure. The specimen is then unloaded and allowed to heal for 48 hours. The healed specimen is then loaded to failure again. The healing efficiency for this specimen is approximately 90%. The dashed line indicates the fracture load of neat epoxy. (b) Effect of microcapsule concentration on virgin fracture toughness.

Optimization of the materials system for maximum healing efficiency is an on-going research goal. Healing efficiency is a complex material property that not only depends on the factors listed above, but on their interplay *in situ*. For example, the healing kinetics must be sufficiently rapid so that the healing agent does not have time to diffuse into the surrounding polymer matrix, but slow enough to allow homogeneous mixing of the catalyst and monomer. Both catalyst concentration and temperature significantly affect the rate of healing, and subsequently, the healing efficiency.

In addition to their role in self-healing, embedded microcapsules provide a unique toughening mechanism for epoxy. The effect of microcapsule concentration on the virgin fracture toughness of epoxy is shown in Fig. 4b. Maximum toughening of about 130% is obtained between 10-20 wt% depending on the size of the microcapsules. Examination of the fracture surfaces and comparisons to other particulate reinforcements have revealed that the microcapsules provide toughening through a combination of crack pinning and localized plastic deformation [10]. Recognizing that the inherent toughness of the epoxy is increased by the addition of microcapsules, the self-healed results in Fig. 4a recover at a level of 115% when compared to the virgin neat resin toughness.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Optimization of healing efficiency will require a more thorough understanding of the complex interplay between factors that influence healing kinetics. Research is on going to measure the *in situ* healing kinetics and the influence of catalyst concentration. Subsequent generations of self-healing polymers will incorporate more robust and active catalyst-healing agent materials systems with increased tolerance to thermal and environmental extremes. The future goals in this emerging field of research will include microcirculatory systems to replenish the supply of healing agents and catalysts to the host material.

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REFERENCES

- [1] White, S.R., Sottos, N.R., Geubelle, P.H., Moore, J.S., Kessler, M.R., Sriram, S.R., Brown, E.N., and Viswanathan, S., "*Autonomic healing of polymer composites*," *Nature*, 409, 794-797 (2001).
- [2] Talrega, R. (1989). *J. Strain Anal. Eng. Des.* 24, 215.
- [3] Talrega, R. (Ed) (1994). *Damage Mechanics of Composite Materials*. Elsevier, New York.
- [4] Gamstedt, E. K. and Talrega, R. (1999). *J. Mat. Sci.* 34, 2535.
- [5] Pecht, M. G., Nguyen, L. T., and Hackim, E. B. (1995). *Plastic-Encapsulated Microelectronics*. John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- [6] Lee, L. H. (1991). *Adhesive Bonding*. Plenum Press, New York.
- [7] M.R. Kessler and S.R. White, "Self-activated healing of delamination damage in woven composites," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 32(5), 2001, pp. 683-699.
- [8] M.R. Kessler and S.R. White: "Cure kinetics of the ring-opening metathesis polymerization of dicyclopentadiene", *Journal of Polymer Science: Part A: Polymer Chemistry*, 40(14), 2002, pp. 2373-2383.
- [9] Brown, E.N., Sottos, N.R., and White, S.R., "*Fracture testing of a self-healing polymer composite*," *Experimental Mechanics*, 42 (4), 372-379 (2002).

- [10] Brown, E.N., Sottos, N.R., and White, S.R., "Microcapsule induced toughening in a self-healing polymer composite," submitted for publication in *Journal of Materials Science* (2003).
- [11] Brown, E.N., Kessler, M.R., Sottos, N.R., and White, S.R., "In situ poly(urea-formaldehyde) microencapsulation of dicyclopentadiene," *Journal of Microencapsulation* (2003), in press.
- [12] M.R. Kessler, N.R. Sottos, and S.R. White, "Self-healing structural composite materials," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, in press, 2003.
- [13] Schwab, P., Grubbs, R. H., and Ziller, J. W. (1996). *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 118, 100.
- [14] Jud, K. and Kausch, H.H. (1979) *Polymer Bulletin*. 1, 697.
- [15] Wool, R.P. and O'Conner, K.M. (1982). *Journal of Applied Physics*. 52, 5953.